

BLACK MEMORIES OF THE TECHNICIAN COURSE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT THE FEDERAL TECHNICAL SCHOOL OF SÃO LUÍS-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980)

MEMORIAS NEGRAS DEL CURSO DE TÉCNICO EN EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA EN LA ESCUELA
TÉCNICA FEDERAL DE SÃO LUÍS-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980)

MEMÓRIAS NEGRAS DO CURSO DE TÉCNICO EM EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA DA ESCOLA TÉCNICA
FEDERAL DE SÃO LUÍS-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980)

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Abstract

This article deals with the Technical Course in Physical Education at the Federal Technical School of São Luís-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980). It is inspired by the habitus concept present in the work of Pierre Bourdieu (2008) and Norbert Elias (2002). Its source of research was the documentary, imagery and oral memory of black social agents who experienced the pedagogical practice. A course was identified aimed at black social agents from the Maranhão-JEM'S school games, who wanted to work in the professional sports field of Maranhão, but without the symbolic, social and economic capital required in the local and non-local Higher Education Institutions-IES, revealing so much more about your time.

Keywords: Memorie; Blacks in physical education; Handball; Gym Ronald Carvalho.

Resumen

Este artículo trata sobre el Curso Técnico en Educación Física en la Escuela Técnica Federal de São Luís-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980). Se inspira en el concepto de habitus presente en la obra de Pierre Bourdieu (2008) y Norbert Elias (2002). Su fuente de investigación fue la memoria documental, imaginaria y oral de agentes sociales negros que vivieron la práctica pedagógica. Se identificó un curso dirigido a agentes sociales negros de los juegos escolares de Maranhão-JEM'S, que querían actuar en el campo deportivo profesional de Maranhão, pero sin el capital simbólico, social y económico requerido en las Instituciones de Educación Superior locales y no locales- IES, revelando mucho más sobre su tiempo.

Palabras clave: Memoria; Negros en educación física; Balonmano; Gimnasio Ronald Carvalho.

Resumo

O presente artigo versa sobre o Curso de Técnico em Educação Física da Escola Técnica Federal de São Luís-MA/ETFMA (1970-1980). Inspira-se no conceito habitus presente na obra de Pierre

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Bourdieu (2008) e Norbert Elias (2002). Teve como fonte de pesquisa a memória documental, imagética e oral dos agentes sociais negros que vivenciaram a prática pedagógica. Identificou-se um curso voltado para agentes sociais negros oriundos dos jogos escolares maranhense-JEM'S, que desejavam atuar no campo esportivo profissional maranhense, mas sem capital simbólico, social e econômico exigidos nas Instituições Ensino Superior-IES local e não local, descortinando assim, muito mais sobre o seu tempo.

Palavras-chave: Memória; Negros na educação física; Handebol; Ginásio Ronald Carvalho.

Introduction

In the 1980s, the Federal Technical School of Maranhão (ETFMA) of São Luís - MA offered a technical-pedagogical training course called Technical Course in Physical Education. It aimed to expand the formation of instructors and teachers working in sports grounds and schools. Starting from this place/time/institution of pedagogical practice, this article deals, under a look of memory *habitus*, Physical Education Training based on individuals, content and methods in circulation in the Course.

The course, in this period, achieved expressiveness for Physical Education, building representations about the formation and teaching of this important curricular component. There were five classes, selected annually, with an average duration of two years. In this investigation we sought to know the minutiae of this course: the place of classes, organizing teachers, teachers invited to teach classes, the profile of the participating student, the pedagogical curricular organization, the supports and political-administrative-financial supports, the subjects of the curriculum selected in each edition of the course, among others. By the investigation of these components, it was possible to identify the project that built the pedagogical *habitus* Physical Education in São Luís, to know the organizing entities of the course and subsequent actions.

The study is part of a doctoral research program in Physical Education of the Superior School of Physical Education (ESEF)/Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), whose thesis is entitled BLACK SOCIAL MEMORY OF HANDEBALL IN BRAZIL: experience of social agents of the Maranhão sports field at the Ronald de Carvalho Sports Gym in São Luís-Ma, ongoing at ESEF/UFPEL. In this institutional place of research, sociocultural studies on leisure, sports and health are also fed by the richness of social memory studies.

The *corpus* from the documentary memory created incorporated sources of diverse nature, such as: lesson plans, curriculum, information folder, planning notebooks, photographs, newsletters, newspapers. In the action of crossing between documentary and oral memory, oral statements constituted the reflections, since it is relevant to give voice, hearing and centrality to the reports of black social agents who, in some way, experienced the course, granting visibility to their different interpretations about the experience and ratifying the assumption that forgetting, remembering, erasing, silencing and reconstructions are predilections of each individual. The printed memory interacted with the interviews, this methodological procedure ensured that the interviewed collaborators, about what was experienced in this course, use subjective meanings about it. In this affective and rational choice, a distinct look at the materialized is constructed (Thompson; Frisch; Hamilton, 2002).

Transforming the examination of *corpus* from the research in a written text of Social Memory, the possibility of reconstructing and perceiving the *habitus sportivus* from this period of Physical Education in São Luís-MA, which was linked to the percepts of a sportive physical education, linked to medical and military institutions, already reiterated by historiography. It seemed noteworthy the inexpressive presence of professionals with higher education and the expressive presence of black social agents wanting to act professionally in the sports field, but without technical training. As discussed in this article, the construction of a *habitus* of Physical Education guided by principles and sports practices that guided the specific pedagogical model, with a sport profile, which emphasized a sports education, an aspect highlighted by the syllabus and by teachers and students who are members of the "contest". Another relevant aspect was the interdependence, propagated in the capital and in the cities of the municipalities of the countryside of Maranhão. This pedagogical construction of School Physical Education was carried out in different educational places, such as sports squares, recreational streets (leisure) and clubs. We also tried to show that the course was a time and space of movement of teachers and students of different social and racial *habitus*, that came from different places, and of practices of transmission and dissemination of ideas, concepts, practices and educational values still poorly explored by the social memory of Brazilian Physical Education of the last decades of the twentieth century.

The Three Editions of Physical Education Technician Course of ETFMA/CEFETMA

The creation of the Physical Education Teacher Course at the Second Grade level for the exercise of first grade teaching at the Federal Technical School of Maranhão (ETFMA), was designed by professor Laércio Elias Pereira, who together with teachers Lino Castellini Filho and Sidney F. Zimbers, experienced in previous years in the creation of courses, as the short degree at the Technological Institute of Learning (TIL), based on the model of the Physical Education Course at the University of São Paulo (USP) (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

According to José Maranhão Penha, handball teacher at ETFMA and handball discipline of the course under analysis, the pedagogical training of the physical education technician course at ETFMA began with Laércio, Lino and Manuel Trajano Dantas Neto, who were the mentors and fought hard to implement the course, which had several classes in the morning, afternoon and evening;

[...] and at the beginning of the course I was the teacher of the disciplines Organization, sports administration and handball. I had here the relationship of some classes, people who took the course were interested. A lot of people came. People from the interior of the state. A lot of people entered the selection, those guys who were interested in and liked sports in the countryside, came to acquire knowledge, to enable themselves to develop more physical activity in the interior of the state. The only one who used to indicate was the mayor, he sent the cook, the maid, relatives, his nephew and his acquaintances, and this caused the essence of the goal of the course to be lost. I remember that there was a time that the ETFMA made an agreement with the State Department of Education, then the decay of the course began, the Department of Education provided logistics, material, water, electricity, paper these things, chalk. At the time it was in chalk, ball, and ETFMA provided the teachers, then it fell into decay! Then the Physical Education Division of the State Department of Education was created, coordinated by Lessy Batista Neves. The secretary was Leda Tajara, but they left, and the course fell into decay. It was when the physical education teacher from Maranhão, graduated from UFMA, took it over, Silvana Farias. It began to have some difficulties in fulfilling what was promised, there is no paper, there is no this and that, there is no ball, the teachers were from ETFMA so, they were all there and went to the end. The curriculum was very well structured, it was similar to the UFMA, so that the majority of the students who left the Physical Education course at FTSM, did the PE course at UFMA. The course was the same as UFMA, and the teachers were Laercio, Laercio's wife, Pascoal, both were from ETFMA and UFMA, the curriculum and didactics were the same from UFMA, the entire complete course, but the ETFMA course enabled to teach until Elementary School today, which was the 8th grade at the time, the qualification was until that (José Maranhão Penha).

Seeking to fulfill the goal of offering educational activities of ETFMA, teachers Lino Castellani Filho - the first coordinator of the course, Guaraci Martins Figueiredo and Leopoldo Gil Dúlcio Vaz, Laércio Elias Pereira, Antônio Maria Zacharias Bezerra de Araújo (professor Dimas) all from ETFMA and UFMA, imbued themselves with this objective of concretizing the idea of the Physical Education Course at Technical School of Maranhão (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

In the speech of the IFMA physical education teacher, Vespasiano da Hora, the Association of Physical Education, Sport and Leisure Professionals of Maranhão (APEFELMA), the Department of Education and Federal Center for technological education of Maranhão (CEFET-MA), at the time, held a partnership:

There was an agreement of the secretary of state that was exactly to minimally qualify professionals who were already in the market, in schools, both in the municipality and in the state, working as Physical Education professionals, but who were not licensed, they would need to have the course that would take them out of illegality, to train. Physical Education teachers need to be trained to work in schools. But what to do with people who are already working in school, due to the need and the insufficiency of professionals in the field without higher education? Then the secretary of state for Education through the division of Physical Education, if memory serves me correctly, coordinated at the time by Lessy Batista Neves, signed this agreement between the state and CEFET-MA, had the ability to make this decision, because it was an autarchy at the time, being in charge of the Coordination of this course professor Manuel Trajano, on the CEFET side, so the classes were structured, there were even several sports, such as handball and entered the fights, judo, capoeira, was where I taught: judo, capoeira and volleyball, those were the three of my responsibility and had so many other teachers teaching there, so the purpose was that, to qualify the existing professionals (Vespasiao da Hora).

The pedagogical training of professionals was a banner to fight for, said Vespasiano da Hora:

Exactly, because it was pressured, these professionals cannot be working, they must have training, etc. So this agreement, by this tension, is not a purely thing, let's empower, no! It was pressured, because it had the stamp of illegality, but that was forgiven by the coordination. Look, these people were appointed, there were no physical education teachers, they took the minimum course, which gave them the condition to work, so they will get this course, focused on this audience. The course had a positive effect, it was one of the interesting things that I considered, because those professionals were going to remain there, they could not dismiss them, the maximum that, look, the law does not allow you to stay here, you would enjoy other activities, but do we fire? No! It then qualifies the comrade solely to exercise the activity (Vespasiano da Hora).

In the speech, the course would expand the pedagogical function of the ETFMA, which through training in Physical Education, would participate in solving problems in the area in Maranhão. The field and sportive *habitus* in Maranhão were transforming, however, at the time, the training of professionals in PE and sports was experiencing many difficulties. At UFMA, in the physical education course, we lived with the absence of teachers with Masters and Doctorates and the lack of students in the undergraduate program. Thus, the institution did not train any teacher each year; a frustrating attempt was the unsuccessful implementation of Physical Education Course at UEMA, the completion of the technical course of Physical Education at ITA. In the same context, in a study carried out in 1982, it was found that only in the Department of Education of the state of Maranhão there was a deficit of 980 Physical Education teachers in the school network (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

In 2002, professor Leopoldo Gil reported to the Secretary of State for Sports and Leisure (SEDEL) the deficit of Physical Education teachers in the state of Maranhão, as justification for recreating the Physical Education Course at UEMA. In view of the lagging context regarding the supply of professionals in the Maranhão sports field, professor Leopoldo Gil reaffirmed:

It still exists, it's more advanced... There were approximately 2,300 contract teachers, such as Physical Education teachers, of whom approximately 1,900 were laymen, of these 400 teachers, 5 years ago. Until today there is this, the Department of Education, when it enters this scheme of Education Statistics, you will have approximately 2,000 teachers hired or appointed Physical Education teacher, without any link to Physical Education. They have no training in Physical Education until nowadays, the state claims lay personnel are occupying, not retiring. In Santa Helena-MA in the holm of Maranhão, it has 120 teachers..., 120 laity and the state school that had been there, it's closed... No graduates, 120 lay people... They're election cables, they've been hired. In São Luís-MA, do you want to see something at Liceu of Maranhão? Raise the staff of teachers, half of them do not have a Physical Education course, those who have, have the technical school course, they're qualified until the 6th grade, Luís Reis de França Martins, they're part of those 107 teachers who are working, Gastão, all these old people who are there, do not have a physical education course.

Although the ETFMA had a good infrastructure to offer the physical education course, there were not the necessary financial resources for the purchase of equipment, remuneration of personnel and acquisition of teaching materials for the operation of the course. In the effort to continue the course, some partnerships were needed with SEDEL and Education, both from the state of Maranhão, as well as the municipal Department of Education of São Luís - MA and the National Sports Council (CND) (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

For professor Leopoldo Gil, the CND sports squares project was fundamental in the implementation of the Technical Course in Physical Education at ETFMA, in order to train the professionals of the municipalities contemplated by the project:

The first physical education technician course was for the National Sports Council – CND, this had a project of sports squares in several municipalities in Brazil, and to Maranhão came 45 squares, but mandatorily, they had to have a Physical Education professional to coordinate the activities, and Maranhão did not have, so the CND agreed with the ETFMA to train these personnel in the city hall of the interior of the state, the 45 city halls were going to indicate a professional to come and do the course lasting 1 year, 8 hour class per day, morning and afternoon, to be able to train these personnel in 1 year in technical, the workload was at least 1,800 hours, thus it was possible to do in 1 year, 8 hours of daily activities, 10 hours classes per day, it was possible to fulfill the 1,800 , hours only that the state city halls, signed the contract with CND only, there was no one to come (Leopoldo Gil).

For Leopoldo Gil, the CND coexisted with SEDEL, which was executing the project, since the president of the CND was the secretary of SEDEL, this Department not only took notice, but also indicated who would come to take the course. The Physical Education Technician course followed the same model recommended by UFMA, being a pioneer in Maranhão, formed groups of teachers mostly from *black social and racial habitus*, a repressed demand of the time, mainly from former Black Athletes from the handball area who played at the Ronald Carvalho gymnasium during the Maranhão School Games (JEMs) (1970-1980), which at that time, already reached the participation of more than three thousand students, consolidating itself as the largest event in the Maranhão sports calendar (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

That said, the ETFMA course was the pedagogical experience of *habitus* individual and collective, of a group of teachers led by professors Lino Castellani Filho, Laércio Elias Pereira and Manoel Trajano who transformed the *the habitus sports field* of Maranhão, in the way of thinking, acting and feeling in the construction of the course curriculum to face the demands of the time. The first edition of the course ran for two years, divided into two parts: General Training, lasting one year, and specific training, taken in the other remaining year. In the final phase, the teacher chose the qualification among those offered in the course (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

The structure of the course was interdisciplinary, had a solid scientific basis, was practically guided by the same curricular structure of the course of the Department of Physical Education of UFMA. With engaged, experienced teachers and socio-educational trajectories in the vast frames of renowned teaching intuitions: ETFMA and UFMA, which leads us to believe that this was a strategy of the social agents of the sports field to overcome the gaps in the training of Physical Education teachers in Maranhão, due to the lack of number of students in classrooms of the UFMA Physical Education course and the absence of professionals in this field in the state (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

From 1980, the Technical Course in Physical Education of the ETFMA began to gain prominence in the game established among the educational institutions of Maranhão, the "disputes" in the field began to become evident when establishing comparisons between the courses. It was a pedagogical practice of a concrete experience for a group of black social agents, from the most vulnerable layers of the social field, with little economic and educational capital, which made it difficult to pass the entrance exam of the time or attend the Physical Education Course in another Brazilian city, in the case of Belém-PA, Campina Grande or Rio de Janeiro-RJ, the most common scripts of individuals with social, economic and educational capital from the favored layers of the social field of Maranhão.

It should be noted that the pedagogical proposal has changed and transformed the professional sports field in Maranhão. The black social agents who attended, really wanted to transform the field of Physical Education and Sports. In the words of Leopoldo Gil this is clear:

The course was really superior to the UFMA course, because we only had physical education students, we did not have students who took the entrance exam for Medicine, Pharmacy, Biochemistry, so much so that the good students who left this technical course, and then took the entrance exam, were approved, and constituted themselves in one of the best classes that UFMA ever had, it was precisely at the time when there was the unlinking for internal transfer of course within the university, that is, the student at the end of the integrated basic period of health courses, could not ask for transfer to another course from this area such as Medicine, Dentistry, Pharmacy and Nursing. There was no second option anymore, if the candidate took the entrance exam for Physical Education, it was Physical Education and that's it, although there were many people who could not be approved for Medicine, they persisted in taking the entrance exam for Physical Education, and soon after gave a way and transferred to another course, because Physical Education, previously, was still linked to the medical area, we have as an example, the case of Paulão, he finished Physical Education and went to do Dentistry right after. He transferred, and took the two courses, completed one and then went to complete the other [...].

The participation of teachers from São Paulo in Physical Education, in the Constitution of the course, should be praised. The political-pedagogical commitment of this faculty was evident, since when they landed here, doing justice to what they came to do in Maranhão. Possessors of a vast cultural and technical-scientific capital at that time, with higher education in the field of Physical Education, in the best Higher Institutions of Physical Education in Brazil, such as the Army Superior School in Physical Education, Gama Filho and USP.

When it was established in 1980, the physical education course lasted eight months, full-time, with eight hours/class per day. The financial resources base of the federal government worked, through the agreement SEDEL / CND / Secretariat of Education of the municipality of São Luís - MA. A class with 40 students, half of the students indicated by SEDEL, and the other indicated by the CND the interior city halls of Maranhão, being in the end, the indication of all students under the responsibility of SEDEL (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

The CND negatively evaluated the partnership during the course. "The mayors diverted the funds received to finance the construction of the CND Sports Parks". Thus, the CND denounced the agreement and suspended the payment due to SEDEL's lack of accountability. This took over the course in its entirety, and later incorporated all the conclusives as employees of the department (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

During the administration of Secretary Elir Jesus Gomes, together with SEDEL, the first installment of the financial resource was released for the Constitution of the Physical Education Course at ETFMA. The second part is released *a posteriori*, during half of the course, for the construction of sports centers; there would be 40 municipalities benefited, but only half indicated candidates for the course in São Luís – MA. Of the 20 municipalities, not all the money was released (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

Profile of the Physical Education Technician Course of ETFMA /CEFETMA

When characterizing the ETFMA Physical Education Technician Course, the explanatory note advised that Physical Education teacher in the exercise in the 1st grade should have general and specific knowledge, conditioning and motor skills, patience, liking children and vocation to teaching in the 1st grade, when "children from 7 to 12 years old

begin to practice Physical Education, recreational, sports in various modalities". The Physical Education Teacher, in the exercise of the 1st grade, carried out his activities in 1st grade schools (from 1st to 6th grades) of Municipal, State and Private educational networks, in special classes, in recreational clubs and recreation centers. The objective of the course was to provide the student with a theoretical-practical training necessary for the satisfactory performance of the profession, by legally enabling them to exercise the profession of technician of 2nd degree in one of the qualifications offered by the ETFMA (Escola Técnica Federal do Maranhão, 1990).

The pedagogical curricular proposal of the ETFMA course was structured in two blocks: General Training and specific training. Specialization or qualification in sports was provided for in the course project and curriculum. The curricular structure foreseen for 1980 aimed at a generalist qualification, in which most of the subjects were of broad training (Technical Federal School of Maranhão, 1990).

The subjects of the initial curricular structure of the first class of teachers in Physical Education, in 1980, were ordered by area, with ten in the general training: writing and expression (60hs); Regional Studies (40hs); organization and administration of Physical Education and sports (60hs); Fundamentals of Education (100hs); Notions of Anatomy (100hs); Notions of Physiology (60hs); Notions of First Aid (60hs); Structure and Functioning of 60hs); Applied Statistics (40hs); Didactics (120hs) in a total of 700hs. In the area of special training were ten: Gymnastics (140hs); swimming (80hs); Athletics (100hs); Games and Recreation (120hs); Olympic Gymnastics (80hs); *Handball (80hs)*; Volleyball (80hs); Basketball (80hs); Judo (60hs); Football (60), totaling 880hs; supervised internship. The course was taught on a full-time basis to holders of 2nd degree courses, now called subsequent (Technical Federal School of Maranhão, 1990).

In 1982, in the second edition of the course, the agreement was made directly between the parties of the SEDEL/Department of Education/department of Education of the municipality of São Luís - MA. There were 80 students, in two classes, one in the morning shift and the other in the evening, with the purpose of training sports and Recreation technicians from SEDEL, and teachers from the state and municipal Education Departments of São Luís - MA. SEDEL has never appealed to the ETFMA. This had to take over all the development and completion of the course. Thus, the partnership between ETFMA/SEDEL ended (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

The same form of curricular organization was maintained and the workload of some subjects was increased in general education in 1982: Writing and Expression (60hs); Regional Studies (30hs); Fundamentals of Education (60); Notions of Anatomy (90hs); Notions of Physiology (60hs); Notions of First Aid (60hs); Athletics (120hs); Organization and Administration of Physical Education and Sports (60hs), Games and Recreation (90hs); Didactics (120hs). In specific training: Basketball (90hs); Soccer (60hs); Sports Gymnastics (30hs); *Handball* (90hs); Swimming (90hs); Rhythmic (dances) (60hs); Volleyball (90hs); Judo (60hs); Statistics Applied To Physical Education (60hs); Gymnastics (120hs); Structure and Functioning of 1st Grade Education (60hs), totaling 1650hs and more supervised internship. The prerequisite for taking the course continued to be to have second degree completed - General Education (Technical Federal School of Maranhão, 1990, not paged).

In 1983, as a result from the agreement between ETFMA / SEEDUC, the third class of teachers in Physical Education was offered. This time, the Department of Physical Education was recreated, having in its coordination the Physical Education teacher, Silvana Farias. In the new agreement, SEEDUC's counterpart was to provide some teachers and sports equipment, and in the case of ETFMA to cede its physical education teachers and sports facilities and equipment. As in the previous times, the financial resource was not transferred to ETFMA, although the institution provided all the service, and once again the school did not receive the money for the execution of the pedagogical project developed (Vaz; Araújo, 2014).

In 1983, the class of the course worked in the daytime, undergoing curricular modification in number of subjects offered in the areas of General Education (08 subjects): Writing and Expression (60hs); Regional Studies (30hs); Fundamentals of Education (60hs); Notions of Anatomy (90hs); Notions of Physiology (60hs); Notions of First Aid (60hs); Structure and Operation of 1st Grade Education (30hs); Didactics (120hs), with a total of 540 hours. In the special training there was an increase in the number of disciplines in the area of sport, as an outgrowth of the *habitus* sports that had its peak in the 1980s in Brazil: Organization and Administration of Physical Education and Sports (60hs); Gymnastics (120hs); Statistics Applied To Physical Education (60hs); Athletics (120hs);

Games and Recreation (90hs) Teaching Practice (90hs); Basketball (90hs); Soccer (60hs); Sports Gymnastics (30hs); *Handball* (90hs); Volleyball (90hs); Swimming (90hs); Judo (60hs); Rhythmic Dances (60hs), totaling a workload of 1110hs, plus supervised internship. (Technical Federal School of Maranhão, 1990, not paged).

Contents and Knowledge in Transmission in the Physical Education Technician Course of ETFMA/CEFETMA

Several contents were transmitted in the course, leading to believe that in Brazil Physical Education in this period had a diverse *habitus* and themes that were recognized as important for the training and teaching of teachers. Some subjects offered were aimed at the construction of lesson plans and teaching planning, and dealt with children's games and recreation, sports, dances and gymnastics. Others addressed topics related to writing and expression; Regional Studies; Fundamentals of Education; Notions of Anatomy; Notions of Physiology; Notions of First Aid; Structure and Functioning of 1st Grade Education, with supervised internship.

We identified a strong presence of sports content, both individual and collective (Basketball; Soccer; Sports Gymnastics; *Handball*; Swimming; Rhythmic (dances); Volleyball; Judo). We highlight an evidence for the modalities of court, more frequent than individual sports. The disciplines of sports practices were occupying more space during the three editions of the course, punctuating the different ways of approaching them in social, affective, technical, tactical issues, emphasizing the rules, highlighting the educational principles with guiding the teaching of the fundamentals and rules of the modality. Another concern of teachers was learning with pleasure. They hoped that teaching-learning in Physical Education would incorporate in students the desire to practice sports, even in the absence of the teacher. However, there was a divergence in the prescription of students about the age group of entry into sports initiation. For some teachers, the child should enter the sport at the age of 4-6, while others, only from the age of 10.

According to the curriculum reworked for each edition of the course, we can infer that the organizers sought to offer the target audience diversified knowledge and knowledge that incorporated details about the technical dimensions of each action and that were understood as pedagogical and scientifically systematized knowledge and knowledge. The references were linked to the role configured to physical education in the transformations of social and human coexistence. The data allow us to infer the formative intention of the choices, in tune with the guidelines of the organizers who believed they were the most knowledgeable. Thus, when choosing the contents to be taught and the regent teachers, they concretized a selection of educational rules and values among so many principles and other educational codes transmitted in the course, amplifying the understanding about Physical Education, although, for many teachers, education was presented as an action of transmission of content and values (Linhaes, 2006; Lima, 2012).

The investigation allows us to affirm that, in the training offered by the Physical Education Technician Course, there was a solid interaction between practices, contents and individuals, in a constant process of transaction of ideas and pedagogical values. In the 1980s, physical education teachers demanded to interact socio-biological aspects, ensuring a configuration between contents and betting on a systemic formation of the “student or in a “psycho-socio-Morpho-physiological” training process, as they liked to name it” (Linhaes, 2006; Lima, 2012). Both the written and oral memories, through the interviews, we understand the latent desire to strive to the maximum to do the right thing in the context of Physical Education in Maranhão.

Regarding the methodological procedures, we found that the interviews granted by the collaborating teachers José Maranhão Penha, Vespasiano da Hora and the student Alexandre Magno Reis Muniz were important in the construction of these narratives. Black social agents of this socially lived experience, transforming themselves, and the way they look to the past, agreeing with the aspirations they nurture about the present. Our focus was to qualify the narrative of this memory by analyzing and problematizing the sources.

Several themes worked in the context of the course seem to be perpetuated in the present time of School Physical Education: the way of organizing and planning the class, the absence of own material and space in schools, the protuberance of certain physical aspects for the practice of some sports, the recreational profile of classes, games as powerful pedagogical instruments. When we verify these permanences, we consider that it is a predisposition, an inclination, a tendency, which is configured in *sporting habitus*. Thus, such evidence reiterates the understanding that the memory of teacher training and teaching practices selected in São Luís-MA will be better understood with investigations that contemplate “the long duration and that are capable of indicating the meanings conferred on ruptures and continuities” (Lima; Linhales, 2014, p.1518). Reflecting in the present time about the formation of Physical Education Teachers, the authors question: “Are we, teachers and students of Physical Education”, “poorer in communicable experiences, and not richer”? (Benjamin, 1996, P.115).

After reporting in the text the historiographic memory that portrayed the main administrative activities carried out by the organizers of the course, with the primary purpose of constituting the physical education technician course of ETFMA, characterizing at this moment the apprehension of this praxis built by these black social agents of the Maranhão sports field, we understand the *habitus* (Bourdieu, 2004, p.157) as the conception of social principles, which are created by individuals from actions and thoughts. According to the author, the *habitus* it should be understood as “[...] the provisions of the agents [...], in short, these tendencies can be apprehended as inclinations that individuals of a field have about its structure, this implies stating, that by understanding this structural configuration in force within the social field, they will determine which procedures will be implemented within the social field. This point of view of the author is fundamental to apprehend the theme on screen.

In other words, Bourdieu (2008) and Elias (2002) they point out how *habitus* what classical sociology designates as socialization, differentiating the varied forms of learning, among them the primary and the later ways of socialization. *Habitus* for Bourdieu and Elias, it falls within the line of intermediate concepts that fill the mediation between the objective and the subjective, between the institutional and the individual (Setton, 2018).

By understanding this understanding of memory *habitus* incorporated, we infer that the Maranhão sports agents realized how the Maranhão sports field was structured at the end of the last century and through this incorporation, they intended and planned what social practices would be exercised in order to concretize in the future the position of dominance of cultural capital within the social field that the ETFMA/CEFETMA were part of. In this way, we understand the idea and the construction of the Physical Education Technician Course, as a consequence of the *habitus* of the black social agents of the sports field in a certain phase of local historiography.

Given this view, we can cite Setton (2002), who presents an understanding of the notion of *habitus*, dialoguing directly with the above understanding. The author states that the *habitus* it can be understood as the actions, aspirations or choices, individual behaviors do not come from planning or calculations, they are rather results of the relationship between the pressures and stimuli of a context and *habitus*. Resulting from the socio-historical process, *habitus* it is not destiny, it is an open set of disposition, incessantly challenged by new experiences and, in this way, incessantly affected by them (Bourdieu, 2008). Which refers directly to what was explained in the previous paragraph.

When discussing through these authors, we show that the black social agents in Maranhão followed a logical orientation that governed the sports field of Brazilian Physical Education and, according to this organization, planned a strategy that would transform the educational field of Physical Education in Maranhão into one of the main agents of the sports field of Brazilian handball. This strategy was the construction of the physical education technician course at ETFMA, which would make the institution a powerful builder of educational, social (differential component present in the sports field researched) and symbolic capital. This would place the ETFMA and its black social agents in a distinctive position of dominance in the social space of Physical Education in Maranhão. Consecutively, the course organizers built the practices and actions (the memories *habitus* incorporated) for the purpose of transforming the *habitus* of an individual and collective memory of a group of blacks.

Final Remarks

Based on the concept of *habitus*, we can show that the physical education technician course can be understood as an important educational, cultural and social capital that black social agents obtained from ETFMA/CEFETMA in the 1980s, and these Capitals were manifested in various ways within the field of sports and Physical Education, an area in which social agents are inserted through the form of economic, sociocultural and symbolic capital, which allowed black social agents to distinguish themselves within the field of Physical Education and sports in Maranhão, Brazil and worldwide.

It is also important to remember that the organizers of the course carried out a series of practices and actions, in order to build the course, these administrative procedures being understood as a memory *habitus* of black sports social agents. Given what has been stated above, we can infer that this memory *habitus* individual and collective of different individuals and constituent groups of the sports practice field, obey the same *modus operandi*, in some cases.

Thus, we clarify that the concept of *habitus* Bourdieu and Elias, is a theoretical-methodological tool that allowed the presentation of the narrated thesis on the Physical Education Technician Course at the Ronald Carvalho Sports Gym of ETFMA/CEFETMA in the 1980s. Generally speaking, we can say that the notion of *habitus* as a theoretical-methodological instrument in the studies of social memory, it allows the construction of new investigations that reach countless existing issues within the memory of physical education, sports and handball.

Consecutively, numerous problems that arise in the field of memory study can be deciphered in line with the category *habitus* Pierre Bourdieu(2008) and Norbert Elias(2002), which was established in the last century as an important theoretical reference, offering conceptual principles for understanding the various issues present in the most different social fields, as in the scope of culture, politics, education in its transversality, and as in our case, in the study of Physical Education and modern sports in Maranhão.

The actions and strategies of the black social agents in the ETFMA sports gym were varied, with important contributions in the transformation of the *habitus* Maranhão sports field, which formed and consolidated the emergence of the first training course for Physical Education teachers at the second degree level for the exercise of first-degree teaching at ETFMA, in partnership with CND and SEDEL (Ribeiro, 2018).

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